

Bridge – High Performance Computing Cluster for Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University

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Abstract—This report describes the Bridge, a High Performance Computing cluster hosted at Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University.

1 INTRODUCTION

BRIDGE is a homogenous high performance computing cluster owned by Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University (IAU). The cluster has about 800 cores, and is managed by the Scientific and High Performance Computing Center (SHPC) at IAU.

The entire cluster was donated to the university by Saudi Aramco in 2014, and was previously listed in the Top500 website [1]. Only a portion of the cluster was deployed to production in IAU in early 2018, in the data center owned by the Deanship of Information and Communication Technology of IAU.

2 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Bridge is comprised of 100 nodes of Dell PowerEdge 1950, each node is equipped with two sockets of Intel Xeon X5365 CPU, furnished with 8 GiB of RAM. The cluster nodes are connected with a high-bandwidth and low-latency Infiniband Double-Data-Rate interconnect from Cisco.

3 SOFTWARE

Bridge uses the Community Enterprise Operating System (CentOS) 7.1, and job submissions in the cluster are managed by Slurm 17.11.

The cluster hosts a plethora of commercial and open-source scientific software to support and inspire research at IAU, including computational chemistry software (QuantumEspresso, Siesta, VASP, ect.), computational fluid dynamics (OpenFOAM), a wide range of genomic analysis applications, and many others. The cluster uses Singularity containers [2] to manage the user environment. We use Intel Compiler, Intel MPI, gcc and OpenMPI to build the applications in the Bridge.

4 USERS

Bridge can be accessed by all researchers, faculty members

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and students in IAU. Research collaborators from outside the IAU can also be granted access to the cluster.

5 FURTHER INFORMATION

Up-to-date documentation giving a full description of the hardware infrastructure as well as user documentation is available from the SHPC website: <https://hpc.iau.edu.sa>

REFERENCES

- [1] "PowerEdge 1950, Xeon 53xx 3 GHz, Infiniband." TOP500 Supercomputer Sites, <https://www.top500.org/system/176643>
- [2] Kurtzer GM, Sochat V, Bauer MW (2017) Singularity: Scientific containers for mobility of compute. PLOS ONE 12(5): e0177459. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0177459>